

An Investigation into Smarandachely Product Cordial Labeling of Rooted Product of cycle to Complete Graph $C_n \circ K_m$ in Communication Network

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Abstract- The use of mathematics is quite visible in every area of computer science. Mathematics helps in the design, implementation and analysis of algorithms for scientific and engineering applications. Graph theory is an important area in mathematics. This paper explores the use of Smarandachely Product Labeling by labeling the rooted Product of cycle to Complete Graph for the communication Network.

In the context of Smarandachely Product Cordial Labeling, this work investigates the labeling of the Rooted Product of cycle to Complete Graph $C_n \circ K_m$, where $C_{\{n\}}$ times and $K_{\{m\}}$ times. Smarandachely Product Cordial Labeling is defined as a function $f: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ that labels the edges of graph G such that each edge $uv \in E(G)$ has the induced labeling $f(u)f(v)$. $|vf(0) - vf(1)| \geq 2$ and $|ef(0) - ef(1)| \geq 2$ are the restrictions that the labeling must meet. $vf(0)$ and $vf(1)$ stand for the number of vertices with labels 0 and 1, respectively, and $ef(0)$ and $ef(1)$ stand for the number of edges with labels 0 and 1, respectively. This labeling technique for the given graph product is examined in detail in this study along with its viability and ramifications for graph theory.

Key Words- Cordial labeling, Smarandachely product cordial labeling, Rooted Product of cycle to complete Graph.

Introduction- The application of Graph theory in communication Networks introduced by Suman Deswal and Anita Singhrova (2012, pp.1-5). The graph theoretical ideas are used by various computer applications like data mining, image segmentation, clustering, image capturing, networking etc. Graph theory can be used to represent communication networks. A communications network is a collection of terminals, links and nodes which connect to enable telecommunication between users of the terminals. The communication networks can be represented using the various mathematical structures which also help us to compare the various representations based congestion, switch size and switch count. Graphs have an important application in communication networks. Generally vertices in graph represent terminals, processors and edges represent transmission channels like wires, fibers etc. through which data flows.

Graph labeling is an increasingly significant area of research with diverse scientific and technological applications. It plays a crucial role in various domains, including radio astronomy, radar and missile guidance system design, X-ray crystallography for material spectral analysis, communication networks, and transportation systems. In the context of

graph theory, graph labeling involves assigning integers to the edges, vertices, or both components of a graph, based on specific criteria. This process enables the differentiation of adjacent edges or vertices. The concept of graph labeling was first introduced by Rosa (1967, pp. 349-355).

Smarandachely Product Cordial Labeling, initially introduced by Smarandache (1996, pp.1-2-3), investigates the cordial properties of graphs under product operations. The formal definition of Smarandachely Product Cordial Labeling was later established in 2018 by Patel, Prajapati, and Kansagara (2018, pp. 146-159), specifically focusing on the product cordial labeling of extensions of the Barbell Graph. Their research concentrated on the examination of product cordial labeling for graphs derived from various operations applied to the Barbell Graph.

The present study is now focusing on a distinct class of graph, specifically the Rooted Product of cycle to Complete Graphs. Graphs serve as effective models for interconnection networks, where vertices represent processors and edges denote communication links. It introduces a novel interconnection network topology, known as the Rooted Product of cycle to Complete Graph, which adheres to the criteria for Smarandachely Product Cordial Labeling. This labeling scheme imposes specific conditions that the graph must satisfy, contributing to its theoretical and practical applications in network design.

Graphical Representation of communication network-

The discussion refers to nodes (Vertices) and edges of communication Channel- The various terms involved in this context are mentioned below-

1. Intermission- This is the time for a data to travel from one vertex (switch) to the other. One measure of Intermission is the number of vertices (switch) that a data pass through when travelling between the most distant input and output.
2. Congestion: Congestion is defined as the statistic to quantify blockage problem in communication networks. It is largest number of packets (Data) that end up passing through any vertex (switch).

Theorem 1: The Rooted Product of cycle to complete graph $C_n \circ K_m$ admits Smarandachely product cordial labeling, where $m, n \geq 3$.

Proof:

Case1-When m and n both are even

1. Steps to construct a graph $G = C_n \circ K_m$:-
2. First, we join all the vertices of C_n and then the rest vertices of K_m join with the vertices of C_n and with each other and create a cycle and complete graph.
3. Label the Graph $G = C_n \circ K_m$ in the following steps-
 - i. Label all vertices of C_n with (0) respectively.

- ii. Label all vertices of K_m clock wise with $(1,1,1,0,1,1,1,0,.....)$ respectively.

In graph no. 1.1 Graph $C_4 \circ K_4$ is labeled as follows: -

- i. Label all vertices of C_4 with (0) respectively.
- ii. Label all vertices of K_4 clock wise with $(1, 1, 1, 0, 1)$ respectively.

Graph No. 1.1: Smarandachely product Cordial Labeling of $C_4 \circ K_4$ Graph

$$|\sum v_f(0) - \sum v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|4 - 12| \geq 2$$

$$8 \geq 2$$

$$|\sum e_f(0) - \sum e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|16 - 12| \geq 2$$

$$4 \geq 2$$

Sub case I- When $m, n=4, 6, 8, 10,.....$

We apply the condition of Smarandachely product Cordial labeling –

$$|v_f(0) - v_f(1)| \geq 2 \text{ and } |e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

1.1 When $m=4, n=4, 6, 8, 10,.....$

$$\{v(1) = 3n + 6\}$$

$$\{v(0) = n + 2\}$$

$$\{e(1) = 3n + 6\}$$

$$\{e(0)=4n+8\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} |v_f(0)-v_f(1)| &\geq 2 \\ |(n+2)-(3n+6)| &\geq 2 \\ |n-3n+2-6| &\geq 2 \\ |-2n-4| &\geq 2 \\ 2n+4 &\geq 2 \end{aligned}$$

Where $n=2, 4, 6, 8, \dots$

$$\begin{aligned} |e_f(0) - e_f(1)| &\geq 2 \\ |(4n+8)-(3n+6)| &\geq 2 \\ |4n-3n+8-6| &\geq 2 \\ |n+2| &\geq 2 \\ n+2 &\geq 2 \end{aligned}$$

Where $n=2, 4, 6, 8, \dots$

1.2 When $m=6, n=4, 6, 8, 10, \dots$

$$\begin{aligned} \{v(1)=8n+8\} \\ \{v(0)=4n+4\} \\ \{e(1)=12n+12\} \\ \{e(0)=20n+20\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} |v_f(0)-v_f(1)| &\geq 2 \\ |(4n+4)-(8n+8)| &\geq 2 \\ |4n-8n+4-8| &\geq 2 \\ |-4n-4| &\geq 2 \\ 4n+4 &\geq 2 \end{aligned}$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

$$\begin{aligned} |e_f(0) - e_f(1)| &\geq 2 \\ |(20n+20)-(12n+12)| &\geq 2 \\ |20n-12n+20-12| &\geq 2 \\ |8n+8| &\geq 2 \\ 8n+8 &\geq 2 \end{aligned}$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

1.3 When $m=8, n=4, 6, 8, 10, \dots$

$$\begin{aligned} \{v(1)=12n+12\} \\ \{v(0)=4n+4\} \\ \{e(1)=30n\} \\ \{e(0)=28n\} \end{aligned}$$

$$|v_f(0)-v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(4n+4)-(12n+12)| \geq 2$$

$$|4n-12n+4-12| \geq 2$$

$$|-8n-8| \geq 2$$

$$8n+8 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(28n)-(30n)| \geq 2$$

$$|28n-30n| \geq 2$$

$$|-2n| \geq 2$$

$$2n \geq 2$$

Where $n=2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

1.4 When $m=10, n=4, 6, 8, 10, \dots$

$$\{v(1)=14n\}$$

$$\{v(0)=6n\}$$

$$\{e(1)=42n\}$$

$$\{e(0)=50n\}$$

$$|v_f(0)-v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|6n-14n| \geq 2$$

$$|-8n| \geq 2$$

$$8n \geq 2$$

Where $n=2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(50n)-(42n)| \geq 2$$

$$|50n-42n| \geq 2$$

$$|8n| \geq 2$$

$$8n \geq 2$$

Where $n=2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

1.5 When $m=12, n=4, 6, 8, 10, \dots$

$$\{v(1)=18n\}$$

$$\{v(0)=6n\}$$

$$\{e(1)=72n\}$$

$$\{e(0)=62n\}$$

$$|v_f(0) - v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|6n - 18n| \geq 2$$

$$|-12n| \geq 2$$

$$12n \geq 2$$

Where $n=2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(62n) - (72n)| \geq 2$$

$$|62n - 72n| \geq 2$$

$$|-10n| \geq 2$$

$$10n \geq 2$$

Where $n=2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

Case2-When n is even and m is odd-

1. Steps to construct a graph $G = C_n \circ K_m$:-
2. First, we join all the vertices of C_n and then the rest vertices of K_m join with the vertices of C_n and with each other and create a cycle and complete graph.
3. Label the Graph $G = C_n \circ K_m$ in the following steps-
 - i. Label all vertices of C_n with (0) respectively.
 - ii. Label all vertices of K_m clock wise with (1,1,1,0,1,1,1,0.....) respectively.

In graph no. 2.1 Graph $C_4 \circ K_5$ is labeled as follows: -

- i. Label all vertices of C_4 with (0) respectively.
- ii. Label all vertices of K_5 clock wise with (1, 1, 1, 0) respectively.

Graph No. 2.1: Smarandachely product Cordial Labeling of $C_4 OK_5$ Graph

$$|\sum v_f(0) - \sum v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|8 - 12| \geq 2$$

$$4 \geq 2$$

$$|\sum e_f(0) - \sum e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|32 - 12| \geq 2$$

$$20 \geq 2$$

Sub case II- When $m=5, 7, 9$ and $n=4, 6, 8, 10, \dots$

We apply the condition of Smarandachely product Cordial labeling –

$$|v_f(0) - v_f(1)| \geq 2 \text{ and } |e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

2.1 When $m=5, n=4, 6, 8, 10, \dots$

$$\{v(1) = 6n\}$$

$$\{v(0) = 4n\}$$

$$\{e(1) = 6n\}$$

$$\{e(0) = 16n\}$$

$$|v_f(0) - v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|4n-6n| \geq 2$$

$$|-2n| \geq 2$$

$$2n \geq 2$$

Where $n=2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(16n)-(6n)| \geq 2$$

$$|16n-6n| \geq 2$$

$$|10n| \geq 2$$

$$10n \geq 2$$

Where $n=2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

2.2 When $m=7, n=4, 6, 8, 10, \dots$

$$\{v(1)=10n\}$$

$$\{v(0)=4n\}$$

$$\{e(1)=20n\}$$

$$\{e(0)=24n\}$$

$$|v_f(0)-v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|4n-10n| \geq 2$$

$$|-6n| \geq 2$$

$$6n \geq 2$$

Where $n=2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(24n)-(20n)| \geq 2$$

$$|24n-20n| \geq 2$$

$$|4n| \geq 2$$

$$4n \geq 2$$

Where $n=2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

2.3 When $m=9, n=4, 6, 8, 10, \dots$

$$\{v(1)=12n\}$$

$$\{v(0)=6n\}$$

$$\{e(1)=30n\}$$

$$\{e(0)=44n\}$$

$$|v_f(0)-v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|6n-12n| \geq 2$$

$$|-6n| \geq 2$$

$$6n \geq 2$$

Where $n=2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(44n-1)-(30n)| \geq 2$$

$$|44n-30n| \geq 2$$

$$|14n| \geq 2$$

$$14n \geq 2$$

Where $n=2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

Case3-When n is odd and m is odd-

1. Steps to construct a graph $G = C_n \circ K_m$:-

2. First, we join all the vertices of C_n and then the rest vertices of K_m join with the vertices of C_n and with each other and create a cycle and complete graph.

3. Label the Graph $G = C_n \circ K_m$ in the following steps-

- i. Label all vertices of C_n with (1) respectively.
- ii. Label all vertices of K_m anti clock wise with (1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0.....) respectively.

In graph no. 3.1 Graph $C_3 \circ K_5$ is labeled as follows: -

- i. Label all vertices of C_3 with (1) respectively.
- ii. Label all vertices of K_4 anti clock wise with (1, 0, 1, 0) respectively.

Graph No. 3.1: Smarandachely product Cordial Labeling of $C_3 \circ K_5$ Graph

$$|\sum v_f(0) - \sum v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|6-9| \geq 2$$

$$6 \geq 2$$

$$|\sum e_f(0) - \sum e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|21-12| \geq 2$$

$$11 \geq 2$$

Sub case III- When $m=5,7,9,11,\dots$, $n=3,5,7,9,11,\dots$

We apply the condition of Smarandachely product Cordial labeling –

$$|v_f(0)-v_f(1)| \geq 2 \text{ and } |e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

3.1 When $m=5$ and $n=3, 5, 7, 9,\dots$

$$\{v(1)=3n\}$$

$$\{v(0)=2n\}$$

$$\{e(1)=8n+4\}$$

$$\{e(0)=14n+7\}$$

$$|v_f(0)-v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|2n-3n| \geq 2$$

$$|-n| \geq 2$$

$$n \geq 2$$

Where $n=3, 5, 7, 9,\dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(14n+7)-(8n+4)| \geq 2$$

$$|14n-8n+7-4| \geq 2$$

$$|6n+3| \geq 2$$

$$6n+3 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6,\dots$

3.2 When $m=7$ and $n=3, 5, 7, 9,\dots$

$$\{v(1)=8n+4\}$$

$$\{v(0)=6n+3\}$$

$$\{e(1)=12n+6\}$$

$$\{e(0)=32n+16\}$$

$$|v_f(0)-v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(6n+3)-(8n+4)| \geq 2$$

$$|6n-8n+3-4| \geq 2$$

$$|-2n-1| \geq 2$$

$$2n+1 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4,\dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(32n+16)-(12n+6)| \geq 2$$

$$|32n-12n+16-6| \geq 2$$

$$|20n+10| \geq 2$$

$$20n+10 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$

3.3 When $m=9$ and $n=3, 5, 7, 9, \dots$

$$\{v(1)=10n+5\}$$

$$\{v(0)=8n+4\}$$

$$\{e(1)=22n+11\}$$

$$\{e(0)=52n+26\}$$

$$|v_f(0)-v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(8n+4)-(10n+5)| \geq 2$$

$$|8n-10n+4-5| \geq 2$$

$$|-2n-1| \geq 2$$

$$2n+1 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(52n+26)-(22n+11)| \geq 2$$

$$|52n-22n+26-11| \geq 2$$

$$|30n+15| \geq 2$$

$$30n+15 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$

3.4 When $m=11$ and $n=3, 5, 7, 9, \dots$

$$\{v(1)=12n+6\}$$

$$\{v(0)=10n+5\}$$

$$\{e(1)=32n+16\}$$

$$\{e(0)=80n+40\}$$

$$|v_f(0)-v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(10n+5)-(12n+6)| \geq 2$$

$$|10n-12n+5-6| \geq 2$$

$$|-2n-1| \geq 2$$

$$2n+1 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(80n+40)-(32n+16)| \geq 2$$

$$|80n-32n+40-16| \geq 2$$

$$|48n+24| \geq 2$$

$$48n+24 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$

3.5 When $m=13$ and $n=3, 5, 7, 9, \dots$

$$\{v(1)=14n+7\}$$

$$\{v(0)=12n+6\}$$

$$\{e(1)=44n+22\}$$

$$\{e(0)=114n+57\}$$

$$|v_f(0)-v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(12n+6)-(14n+7)| \geq 2$$

$$|12n-14n+6-7| \geq 2$$

$$|-2n-1| \geq 2$$

$$2n+1 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(114n+57)-(44n+21)| \geq 2$$

$$|114n-44n+57-21| \geq 2$$

$$|70n+35| \geq 2$$

$$70n+35 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$

Case4-When n is odd and m is even-

1. Steps to construct a graph $G = C_n \circ K_m$:-

2. First, we join all the vertices of C_n and then the rest vertices of K_m join with the vertices of C_n and with each other and create a cycle and complete graph.

3. Label the Graph $G = C_n \circ K_m$ in the following steps-

- i. Label all vertices of C_n with (1) respectively.
- ii. Label all vertices of K_m clock wise with (1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, ...) respectively.

In graph no. 3.1 Graph $C_3 \circ K_4$ is labeled as follows: -

- i. Label all vertices of C_3 with (1) respectively.
- ii. Label all vertices of K_4 clock wise with (1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0) respectively.

Graph No. 4.1: Smarandachely product Cordial Labeling of C_3OK_4 Graph

$$|\sum v_f(0) - \sum v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|3 - 9| \geq 2$$

$$6 \geq 2$$

$$|\sum e_f(0) - \sum e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|9 - 12| \geq 2$$

$$3 \geq 2$$

Sub case IV- When $m = 4, 6, 8, 10, \dots$ And $n = 3, 5, 7, 9, \dots$

We apply the condition of Smarandachely product Cordial labeling –

$$|v_f(0) - v_f(1)| \geq 2 \text{ and } |e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

4.1 When $m = 4$ and $n = 3, 5, 7, 9, \dots$

$$\{v(1) = 6n + 3\}$$

$$\{v(0) = 2n + 1\}$$

$$\{e(1) = 8n + 4\}$$

$$\{e(0) = 6n + 3\}$$

$$|v_f(0) - v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(2n + 1) - (6n + 3)| \geq 2$$

$$|2n - 6n + 1 - 3| \geq 2$$

$$|-4n - 2| \geq 2$$

$$4n + 2 \geq 2$$

Where $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(6n+3)-(8n+4)| \geq 2$$

$$|6n-8n+3-4| \geq 2$$

$$|-2n-1| \geq 2$$

$$2n+1 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

4.2 When $m=6$ and $n=3, 5, 7, 9, \dots$

$$\{v(1)=8n+4\}$$

$$\{v(0)=4n+2\}$$

$$\{e(1)=14n+7\}$$

$$\{e(0)=18n+9\}$$

$$|v_f(0)-v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(4n+2)-(8n+4)| \geq 2$$

$$|4n-8n+2-4| \geq 2$$

$$|-4n-2| \geq 2$$

$$4n+2 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(18n+9)-(14n+7)| \geq 2$$

$$|18n-14n+9-7| \geq 2$$

$$|4n+2| \geq 2$$

$$4n+2 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

4.3 When $m=8$ and $n=3, 5, 7, 9, \dots$

$$\{v(1)=10n+5\}$$

$$\{v(0)=6n+3\}$$

$$\{e(1)=22n+11\}$$

$$\{e(0)=36n+18\}$$

$$|v_f(0)-v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(6n+3)-(10n+5)| \geq 2$$

$$|6n-10n+3-5| \geq 2$$

$$|-4n-2| \geq 2$$

$$4n+2 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(36n+18)-(22n+11)| \geq 2$$

$$|36n-22n+18-11| \geq 2$$

$$|14n+7| \geq 2$$

$$14n+7 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

4.4 When $m=10$ and $n=3, 5, 7, 9, \dots$

$$\{v(1)=12n+6\}$$

$$\{v(0)=8n+4\}$$

$$\{e(1)=32n+16\}$$

$$\{e(0)=60n+30\}$$

$$|v_f(0)-v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(8n+4)-(12n+6)| \geq 2$$

$$|8n-12n+4-6| \geq 2$$

$$|-4n-2| \geq 2$$

$$4n+2 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(60n+30)-(32n+16)| \geq 2$$

$$|60n-32n+30-16| \geq 2$$

$$|28n+14| \geq 2$$

$$28n+14 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

4.5 When $m=12$ and $n=3, 5, 7, 9, \dots$

$$\{v(1)=14n+7\}$$

$$\{v(0)=10n+5\}$$

$$\{e(1)=44n+22\}$$

$$\{e(0)=90n+45\}$$

$$|v_f(0)-v_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(10n+5)-(14n+7)| \geq 2$$

$$|10n-14n+5-7| \geq 2$$

$$|-4n-2| \geq 2$$

$$4n+2 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$

$$|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 2$$

$$|(90n+45)-(44n+22)| \geq 2$$

$$|90n-44n+45-22| \geq 2$$

$$|46n+23| \geq 2$$

$$46n+23 \geq 2$$

Where $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$

Hence the Rooted product of cycle to Complete Graph $C_n \circ K_m$ admits Smarandachely product cordial labeling, where $m, n \geq 3$.

Hence proved.

Conclusion- The application of graph theory in communication networks has been discussed in this graph for the graph Rooted product of cycle to Complete Graph $C_n \circ K_m$. This work investigates the structural features of graphs using Smarandachely Product Cordial Labeling, uncovering new patterns and correlations in the Rooted Product of cycle to Complete Graphs. This study advances the area of graph theory and provides a deeper knowledge of the intricate relationships found in graph structures. It also inspires researchers to build upon these findings and establishes a platform for future study. With regard to the Rooted Product of cycle to Complete Graphs, the study specifically applies Smarandachely Product Cordial Labeling. For the edges of G , the labeling function $f: E(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ is used, and the induced labeling $f(u)f(v)$ on each edge $uv \in E(G)$ satisfies the constraints $|ef(0) - ef(1)| \geq 2$ and $|vf(0) - vf(1)| \geq 2$.

Data Availability-The author declares that there is no data used in the article.

Declarations

Conflict of interest: The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

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